

40 20 0 40 km

▲ archaeological site
— river

— border
● capital
COUNTRY

DEM: Natural Earth 2 v3.2
Admin: The World Bank
Hydro: Natural Earth, OSM

Projection: WGS 1984
Datum: WGS 1984

